

Regional Assessment of the Seagrass *Zostera noltei* Hornem. in the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion (Bioregion 2) for the IUCN Red List ^{1,2}

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PLANTAE - TRACHEOPHYTA - LILIOPSIDA - ALISMATALES - ZOSTERACEAE - *Zostera* - *noltei*

Synonyms: *Zostera noltii* & *Nanozostera noltii*

Common Name(s): Dwarf Eelgrass (English) & Zostère naine (French)

Species code: Zn

Taxonomic Notes: This species belongs to subgenus *Zosterella*, which was previously treated as a separate genus, *Nanozostera* (Tomlinson and Posluzny, 2001), a name no longer accepted. Here it is retained in the genus *Zostera*, following (Les et al., 2002). Further, the orthography "Noltii" was used to honor Ernst Ferdinand Nolte (1791-1875). However, the current International Code of Nomenclature has new regulations among which is not to replace "e" by an "i" at the end of the names. Thus, *noltii* has been corrected to *noltei* for a wide range of taxa including *Zostera*. The new taxonomic name (*noltei*) is currently widely accepted.

¹ This regional assessment does not constitute the global assessment for this species, given that its global distribution is not limited to the Tropical Atlantic Seagrass Bioregion.

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Red List Status

VU - Vulnerable, (IUCN version 3.1)

Extent of Occurrence (EOO) in Bioregion 2= 53453 km²

Area of occupancy (AOO) in Bioregion 2= 427.7 km²

Red List Assessment

Assessment Information

Assessors: El-Hacen Mohamed El-Hacen, Duarte G. Frade, Salomão Bandeira, & Ester Serrão

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Time period assessed: 2007-2020

Assessment Rationale

In Bioregion 2, the largest population of *Zostera noltei* occurs in the northern part of Mauritania especially in the Banc d'Arguin National Park (PNBA) and to a lesser extent in the nearby Baie de l'Étoile near Nouadhibou city (Cunha and Araújo, 2009). The species has also been reported in Saloum Delta of Senegal, in 2019, on muddy and sheltered intertidal areas (Sidi Cheikh et al 2023). The meadows of *Z. noltei* in Saloum Delta are the southernmost limit of this species (Sidi Cheikh et al 2023). The population of Baie de l'Étoile seems to be stable with increasing pressure from pollution resulting from mineral and coastal development in the vicinity (Amadou LY, 2009). The largest population of the region in Banc d'Arguin showed an increase over the last three decades (El-Hacen et al., 2020), although it is decreasing in many places in the parc since 2020. However, *Z. noltei* in its southernmost limit, Bioregion 2, is predicted to suffer in the future from ongoing climate change, especially extreme climate events and sea-level rise. Recent ecological niche models suggest that the entire distribution area in the Tropical Atlantic may be lost by 2050 under the RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 climate change scenarios (Chefaoui et al., 2021), qualifying thus as Vulnerable under criterion E. These projections do not meet the conditions for Vulnerable under criterion A3, as the timeline of these projections (2050) falls beyond the duration of three generations (estimated as 3 years, according to Short et al., 2011). The species therefore meets criterion E for VU in this region, and the criteria for the highest category of threat that the taxon qualifies for, prevails over other criteria. We propose therefore to classify *Zostera noltei* as VU E for Bioregion 2. Globally, its classification will depend on Region 3 assessment. Besides warming, the species appears to be affected by burial and turbidity, particularly linked to dust storms as seen in the Banc d'Arguin (Ester Serrao, unpublished data).

Distribution

Geographic Range

Worldwide, *Zostera noltei* occurs in the eastern Atlantic as well as the Baltic, Mediterranean, Black, Caspian and Aral Seas (IUCN assessment, 2010). *Zostera noltei* also occurs in western Africa in Mauritania, Senegal and in the Canary Islands (IUCN assessment, 2010). The southernmost limit of this species is recorded in Saloum Delta, Senegal (Sidi Cheikh et al 2023). In the previous IUCN global assessment, the species was reported in Cape Verde Islands (IUCN assessment, 2010), but new information from large scale surveys revealed that only the seagrasses *Halodule wrightii* (Creed et al., 2016) and *Ruppia maritima* (Martinez-Garrido et al. 2017) occur in the islands of the country Cape Verde.

Country of occurrence in Bioregion 2

Country	Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality
Mauritania	Extant	Native	-	Resident
Senegal	Extant	Native	-	-

FAO Marine Fishing Areas Bioregion 2

	Presence	Origin	Formerly Bred	Seasonality
34. Atlantic - eastern central	Extant	Native	-	-

Distribution Map

Fig. 1. Map showing the actual distribution of *Zostera noltei* in west Africa (Bioregion 2).

Potential areas of occurrence in Senegal and Gambia

Fig. 2. Map showing shallow mudflats along the Senegambia coast that could potentially be occupied by *Zostera noltei*.

Population

The overall status of the species at the global scale is most likely decreasing (IUCN assessment, 2010). Current Population Trend: Decreasing. However, the regional trend is fluctuating or unknown in some areas. The largest subpopulation in the region occurs in northern Mauritania, particularly in the Banc d'Arguin National Park and near Nouadhibou city in the Baie de l'Étoile (Cunha and Araújo, 2009). The coverage of the species in the Banc d'Arguin National Park has increased significantly over the last three decades (El-Hacen et al., 2020), while the subpopulation in Baie de l'Étoile seems to be stable despite facing increasing pressure from mining pollution and coastal development (Amadou LY, 2009). Subpopulations in Senegal appear to be relatively extensive as well and occur in a landscape of tidal pools together with species of *Halodule wrightii* and *Cymodocea nodosa*, this latter mostly within those tidal pools while *Z. noltei* in outer drier areas (Sidi Cheikh et al 2023). This seascape is similar to the one described for *Z. noltei* meadows in Mauritania (der Laan and Wolff 2006).

Habitat and Ecology

Zostera noltei is a small seagrass species occurring mostly in intertidal but also in some subtidal areas (den Hartog, 1970). It is found in coastal and estuarine areas with soft sediment to a maximum depth of 10 m (IUCN assessment, 2010). The Tropical Atlantic likely represented a refugium for *Zostera noltei* during glacial periods, and the region harbors high genetic diversity (Coyer et al., 2004). In west Africa, the species occurs only in the intertidal zone, and at its lower limit in the transition zone between the intertidal and subtidal. The species can co-occur with *Halodule wrightii* at the edges of subtidal *Cymodocea nodosa* beds (Wolff et al., 1993; der Laan and Wolff 2006, Sidi Sheick et al 2023). Elsewhere, the species has been reported from subtidal, brackish and coastal euryhaline conditions (IUCN assessment, 2010). The highest salinity level tolerated by this species is 54.5‰ (Wolff and Smit, 1990). The highest water temperature in which this species can survive was experimentally and empirically determined to be 37 °C (Massa et al., 2009), although it can withstand higher air temperatures along its range and in the region, temperatures exceed this threshold on many occasions every year (de Fouw et al., 2016). The burial/erosion tolerated by this species is extremely low compared to other seagrass species. The threshold has been estimated to vary between 4 and 8 cm, due to the small size of the species and the lack of vertical rhizomes (Cabaço and Santos, 2007). This threshold can be easily passed in the region, which occurs along the Sahara dust storm highway.

Zostera noltei is a monoecious species, with inflorescences containing both male and female flowers. The flowering season is variable, as mechanical disturbance can induce a greater investment in sexual reproduction and longer fertile periods (Alexandre et al., 2005). Generation time (i.e time from germination until seed production) has been estimated as 1 year (Short et al., 2011), but individual plants can be long-lived and extend over large areas through clonal propagation and the dispersal of plant fragments by oceanic currents (Berković et al., 2018). Some of the larger clones in Mauritania have been estimated to be at least 21 to 42 years old (Coyer et al., 2004).

Threats

The current major threats to West African populations of *Zostera noltei* are climate changes, particularly

warming. Ecological niche models suggest that the entire distribution area in the Tropical Atlantic may be lost by 2050 under the RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 climate change scenarios (Chefaoui et al., 2021). Besides warming, the species appears to be affected by burial and turbidity, namely linked to dust storms (Ester Serrao, unpublished data for Banc d'Arguin). There have been major declines in other regions due to loss of water clarity, coastal development and wasting disease (*Labyrinthula*) (de los Santos et al., 2019; Eriksson et al., 2010; Kastler and Michaelis, 1999). *Zostera noltei* is sensitive to eutrophication (Brun et al., 2002) and is negatively affected by shading (van Lent et al., 1991). *Zostera noltei* is usually outcompeted by macroalgae in nutrient-enriched waters (Grilo et al., 2012). In the Tropical Atlantic, *Z. noltei* recovery after disturbance is extremely slow compared to more northern regions, particularly higher on the intertidal gradients (El-Hacen et al., 2018). West African populations of *Z. noltei* are very sensitive to nutrient loading (El-Hacen et al., 2019) and heat-stress (de Fouw et al., 2016).

Conservation Actions

So far, there are no specific conservation measures for *Zostera noltei*, but the species is listed in the Rio Declaration as diverse habitats in need of protection and monitoring (IUCN assessment, 2010). In West Africa, the species is found in the Banc d'Arguin National Park, Mauritania and in Saloum Delta National Park, Senegal but the other populations occur in non-protected areas.

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